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**PREVALENCE OF BENIGN PROSTATIC
HYPERPLASIA AMONG THE PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN THE OUTDOOR
DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), also called prostate enlargement, is a noncancerous increase in size of the prostate gland. Symptoms may include frequent urination, trouble starting to urinate, weak stream, inability to urinate, or loss of bladder control. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, presence of difficulty urination, occasional obstruction and ultrasound findings were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 100 male patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 61.23±6.12 years. Out of these patients, seven patients were suspected as a case of benign prostatic hyperplasia.

Keyword: Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH)

INTRODUCTION:

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), also called prostate enlargement, is a noncancerous increase in size of the prostate gland. Symptoms may include frequent urination, trouble starting to urinate, weak stream, inability to urinate, or loss of bladder control. Complications can include urinary tract infections, bladder stones, and chronic kidney problems. The cause is unclear. Risk factors include a family history, obesity, type 2 diabetes, not enough exercise, and erectile dysfunction. Medications like pseudoephedrine, anticholinergics, and calcium channel blockers may worsen symptoms. The underlying mechanism involves the prostate pressing on the urethra thereby making it difficult to pass urine out of the bladder. Diagnosis is typically based on symptoms and examination after ruling out other possible causes.

Treatment options include lifestyle changes, medications, a number of procedures, and surgery. In those with mild symptoms weight loss, exercise, and decreasing caffeine intake is recommended. In those with more significant symptoms, medications may include alpha blockers such as terazosin or 5 α -reductase inhibitors such as finasteride. Surgical removal of part of the prostate may be carried out in those who do not improve with other measures. Phytotherapies that have been studied, such as saw palmetto, have not been shown to help. About 105 million men are affected globally. BPH typically begins after the age of 40. Half of males age 50 and over are affected. After the age of 80 about 90% of males are affected. Although prostate specific antigen levels may be elevated in males with BPH, the condition does not increase the risk of prostate cancer (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, presence of difficulty urination, occasional obstruction and ultrasound findings were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and

standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 male patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 61.23 ± 6.12 years. Out of these patients, seven patients were suspected as a case of benign prostatic hyperplasia.

DISCUSSION:

As men age, the enzymes aromatase and 5-alpha reductase increase in activity. These enzymes are responsible for converting androgen hormones into estrogen and dihydrotestosterone, respectively. This metabolism of androgen hormones leads to a decrease in testosterone but increased levels of DHT and estrogen. Both the glandular epithelial cells and the stromal cells (including muscular fibers) undergo hyperplasia in BPH. Most sources agree that of the two tissues, stromal hyperplasia predominates, but the exact ratio of the two is unclear.

Anatomically the median and lateral lobes are usually enlarged, due to their highly glandular composition. The anterior lobe has little in the way of glandular tissue and is seldom enlarged. (Carcinoma of the prostate typically occurs in the posterior lobe – hence the ability to discern an irregular outline per rectal examination). The earliest microscopic signs of BPH usually begin between the age of 30 and 50 years old in the PUG, which is posterior to the proximal urethra. In BPH, the majority of growth occurs in the transition zone (TZ) of the prostate. In addition to these two classic areas, the peripheral zone (PZ) is also involved to a lesser extent. Prostatic cancer typically occurs in the PZ. However, BPH nodules, usually from the TZ are often biopsied anyway to rule out cancer in the TZ. BPH can be a progressive growth that in rare instances leads to exceptional enlargement. In some males, the prostate

enlargement exceeds 200 to 500 grams. This condition has been defined as giant prostatic hyperplasia (GPH) (4-5).

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